

Citation

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Linking supply chain management to business performance: An empirical study on Sri Lankan firms

Abstract

Even though an increasing number of firms have seen Supply Chain Management (SCM) as a major component of competitive strategy for enhanced organizational productivity, very few companies have successfully achieved this. Mentzer et al. (2004) presented a conceptual map highlighting the importance of SCM as an antecedent to performance. Current research attempted to empirically validate this in Sri Lanka by studying 30 Sri Lankan-based supply chains and found evidence of performance enhancement through SCM while identifying industry best practices.

Keywords: operational efficiency, organisational performance, supply chain management, supply chain integration

1. Introduction

Emergence of some vital macro-economic factors such as globalization, focus on core competencies, acknowledgment of dependencies, concentration on customer-driven markets, increased cost competition, and information technology advances, highlighted the importance of the field of Supply Chain Management (SCM) as a strategic tool for competitive advantage (Hammer 2006). However, according to The Annual Global Survey of Supply Chain Progress conducted by Poirier *et al* for 5 consecutive years, very few companies have succeeded in achieving this. Hence, it has become a timely requirement for professionals engaged in managing the supply chain to have a usable knowledge base that can transform their traditional mindsets and help them in preparing a holistic map (a conceptualization) for transforming the supply chain management processes, as mentioned by Mohanty and Deshmukh (2005).

Mentzer *et al.* in 2001 and later in 2004 addressed this issue by introducing a comprehensive conceptual model indicating the nature, antecedents, and consequences of the phenomena, identifying Supply Chain Orientation (SCO) as an antecedent to SCM and enhanced performance as the consequence of SCM. The purpose of this research is to recognize Mentzer *et al.* (2001) 's work by validating the suggested model empirically while identifying industry best practices.

Mentzer *et al.* identified a supply chain as a set of three or more entities (organization or individuals) directly involved in the upstream and downstream flows of products, services, finances, and/or information from source to a customer and managing this chain as “The systemic, strategic coordination of the traditional business functions and the tactics across these business functions within a particular company and across businesses within the supply chain, for the purposes of improving the long-term performance of the individual

companies and the supply chain as a whole” (Mentzer *et al.*, 2001, p. 18). In this, he identified the following SCM activities as essentials to improved performance: information sharing, shared risks and rewards, cooperation, similar customer service goals and focus, integration of key processes, long-term relationships, and inter-functional coordination.

2. Methodology

2.1 The conceptual model and hypotheses

Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework developed for this research, extending Mentzer *et al.* (2004).

Figure 1. Conceptual framework

The present research concentrated on seven sub-hypotheses from the main hypothesis.

H1: SCM directly and positively contributes to business performance.

H1a: Vision and goals directly and positively contribute to business performance

H1b: Information sharing directly and positively contributes to business performance

H1c: Risk and reward sharing directly and positively contributes to business performance

H1d: Cooperation directly and positively contributes to business performance

H1e: Process integration directly and positively contributes to business performance

H1f: Agreed supply chain leadership directly and positively contributes to business performance

H1g: Long-term relationships directly and positively contribute to business performance

2.2 Measures and Data Collection

Measures of all constructs were developed based on extant literature, primarily Mentzer *et al.* (2004). Before deciding the final version of the survey instrument, pretesting was performed to enhance the relevance and clarity of the scale items in relation to the Sri Lankan context, and local professionals with experience in Supply Chain Management functions served as pre-testers. All variables of interest were estimated through respondents' perceptual evaluation on a five-point Likert scale: the response categories for each item were anchored by 1 (strongly disagree) and 5 (strongly agree). Alterations were based on the pretests conducted. Thirty large scale best performing companies from twelve industries were selected as follows; 1) Automotive, 2) Building Materials, 3) Chemicals/Plastics, 4) Computer Hardware, 5) Electronics, 6) Food Related, 7) Metals/Metal Working, 8) Office Equipment, 9) Paper & Packaging, 10) Pharmaceuticals, 11) Textiles/Clothing, and 12) Other.

2.3 Data Analysis

Data analysis was carried out in several steps. As the first step, a basic statistical analysis was conducted to examine for incorrect coding, mean, minimum and maximum values, and standard deviation, and a univariate normal distribution was identified. Secondly, a measurement scale purification of SCM and Performance variables was carried out under validity and reliability testing using Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), and all SCM and performance variables showed high reliability and validity, allowing the researcher to stick to the given set of data. As the next step, the construct SCM was developed using CFA, by loading the seven variables onto one unique first-order factor. The summary of the results is shown in Table 1.

After testing for convergent validity of the seven variables using the correlation coefficient, regression analysis was performed. The results are shown in Table 2. The path from SCM to performance is statistically significant with a fairly strong correlation, with 0.413 R-squared.

Table 1. Summary of results

	Component
Agreed vision	.809
Information sharing	.896
Risk and reward sharing	.761
Cooperation	.901
Integration	.792
Long term relationships	.811
Leadership	.793

Table 2. Regression results

Regression equation	Correlation R	Sign.	R square
$Y = .061 + .631X$.643	.000	.413

3. Discussion of Results

3.1 Findings

The research empirically tested the generalizability of the conceptual model proposed by Mentzer *et al.* (2004) in the Sri Lankan context and revealed that supply chain arrangements are significant in increasing firms' competitive advantage immaterial of the nature of the industry. Several industry best practices were identified, such as: Agreed vision and goals on SCM shared by the whole supply chain - Essential before any SCM project can begin, Sharing information among partners - A prerequisite to implementing a SCM philosophy, Enhancing long-term relationships with supply chain partners - essential to dynamically respond to the needs of end customers in a changing market environment.

3.2 Limitations and future research

As the questionnaire was quite lengthy, the survey was carried out through personal interaction. Hence, only 30 companies were covered. Also, it was evident that different industries possessed different agendas in relation to SCM. Hence, the same questionnaire for all industries failed to address industry-specific details.

In generalizing the findings, it would be very important for future research to use more advanced statistical tools to test the hypothesis, taking a large sample. Also, as Mentzer *et al.* (2004) suggest, the effect of SCM on Performance should be tested not only on single firms but on supply chains, as SCM itself is identified as managing a chain and not a single company.

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